
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ANIMAL AND FLORAL REPRESENTATIONS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FOLK RIDDLES

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Annotation: The article analysis zoonyms and the names of plants used in the riddles of Uzbek and English. It highlights the semantic meanings of the words in the riddles. By comparing two languages, the article uncovers similarities as well as difference between the languages.

Key words: riddles, culture, zoonyms, floral representation, comparative analysis.

Folk riddles, a rich tapestry of linguistic creativity, offer a unique window into cultural perceptions and cognitive processes.[2] By examining the components used to describe animals and floral elements in English and Uzbek folk riddles, we can gain valuable insights into how these cultures conceptualize and categorize the natural world. This analysis will delve into the semantic and cognitive dimensions of these descriptions, exploring the interplay between cultural values, linguistic structures, and cognitive schemas.

In both English and Uzbek folk riddles, animal and floral descriptions often rely on a combination of semantic components, including physical attributes, behavioral characteristics, and cultural associations.[3] These components serve to differentiate one entity from another, highlighting distinctive features that are culturally salient.

Descriptions frequently draw attention to physical characteristics such as size, shape, color, and texture.[1] For instance, an English riddle might describe a rose as "red and thorny," emphasizing its visual appeal and potential danger. Similarly, an Uzbek riddle might characterize a wolf as "gray and fierce," highlighting its predatory nature and physical appearance.

Animal and floral behaviors are often used to create vivid and memorable descriptions. An English riddle might portray a bee as "buzzing and busy," while an Uzbek riddle might depict a sunflower as "turning towards the sun."

Cultural beliefs, myths, and folklore significantly influence the way animals and flowers are described in riddles.[5] For example, in many cultures, the owl is associated with wisdom and knowledge. An English riddle might refer to an owl as "wise and nocturnal," while an Uzbek riddle might emphasize its association with mystical powers. Similarly, the lotus flower is often associated with purity and enlightenment in many cultures, including Uzbek.

The cognitive processes involved in creating and understanding animal and floral descriptions in riddles are complex and multifaceted. Cognitive linguists argue that human cognition is shaped by cultural experiences and embodied knowledge. This perspective suggests that the way we conceptualize and describe animals and flowers is influenced by our interactions with the natural world and our cultural values.

Metaphor and analogy are powerful tools used to create vivid and imaginative descriptions of animals and flowers. In English, a lion might be described as a "king of the jungle," drawing on its perceived dominance and regal status. Similarly, in Uzbek, a rose might be likened to a "heart's desire," emphasizing its beauty and romantic associations.

Cultural schemas, or mental frameworks, guide our understanding of the world and influence the way we interpret information. These schemas are shaped by cultural experiences, beliefs, and values. For example, in many cultures, the horse is associated with freedom, power, and nobility. This cultural schema might be reflected in English and Uzbek riddles that describe horses in heroic or majestic terms.

Cognitive saliency refers to the degree to which a particular feature of an animal or flower is perceived as important or noteworthy.[3] In riddle-making, cognitive saliency plays a crucial role in selecting the most distinctive and memorable features. For instance, the distinctive markings of a zebra or the vibrant colors of a tulip are highly salient features that are often highlighted in riddles.

A comparative analysis of English and Uzbek animal and floral descriptions reveals both similarities and differences in the way these cultures conceptualize and represent the natural world. While both cultures employ similar cognitive strategies, such as metaphor and analogy, there are also cultural variations in the specific components used to describe animals and flowers.

Both English and Uzbek riddles rely on similar cognitive processes, such as metaphor, analogy, and cultural schemas, to create vivid and memorable descriptions. Both cultures frequently use physical attributes, such as size, shape, color, and texture, to differentiate animals and flowers. Both English and Uzbek riddles often incorporate animal and floral behaviors into their descriptions.

The cultural associations attached to animals and flowers can vary significantly between cultures. For example, while the owl is often associated with wisdom in Western cultures, it may have different symbolic meanings in Uzbek culture. Similarly, the lotus flower may hold different cultural significance in English and Uzbek traditions. The linguistic structures used to describe animals and flowers may differ between English and Uzbek. For instance, English riddles often rely on alliteration and rhyme, while Uzbek riddles may employ different poetic devices. The features of animals and flowers that are considered cognitively salient may vary between cultures. For example, while the color of a flower may be a salient feature in one culture, its scent may be more salient in another.

By analyzing the components used to describe animals and floral elements in English and Uzbek folk riddles, we gain a deeper understanding of the cultural and cognitive factors that shape human perception and language use. The interplay between semantic, cognitive, and cultural dimensions reveals the rich tapestry of human thought and expression. Further research in this area could explore the evolution of animal and floral descriptions in riddles over time, as well as the impact of globalization and cultural exchange on these traditional forms of oral literature.

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